

USING ONLINE RESOURCES IN TEACHING PRONUNCIATION TO B1 LEVEL LEARNERS

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As ESL teachers, it is our responsibility to help our students improve their pronunciation.

However, it is also our obligation to teach them how to study and practice independently. Other articles include The 10 Coolest Pronunciation Tools for ESL Students, five mobile apps, and five websites for self-study.

However, the abundance of resources does not stop there. For reference and continuous pronunciation practice, here are some internet tools that every ESL student – and teacher – should use.

Online ESL Pronunciation Practice Resources

1. Pronunciation Guide for Okanagan University College.

This Canadian college provides a complete English pronunciation practice guide organized into 13 units.

Each course focuses on a certain sound or collection of sounds and includes exercises such as video, audio, and dictation to help pupils practice them.

In a dialogue, students have the option of recording their voice. The worksheets for each subject – which are also available in MP3 audio – are very useful for teachers.

2. Phonetics Flash Animation Project at the University of Iowa

A fantastic flash interactive tutorial on American English pronunciation is available from the University of Iowa. It's a comprehensive guide on phonetics, written in a clear, simple style that even ESL students should be able to understand.

Students can use a series of buttons to browse the many features of vowel and consonant sounds, which are taught through animation, sound, and video.

3. The sounds of English.

The website is an excellent resource for learning how to pronounce various English sounds.

The noises are given in pairs (for example, heat and hit); by clicking on each, you may get a description of how each sound is made, as well as video and audio files for each. There's also a "Tips for Teachers" section with some fantastic pronunciation activities for ESL teachers.

4. ESL Center

San Jose City College has an excellent ESL program, which offers an online lab called ESL Station in addition to its normal courses.

Syllables and Stress Patterns, Stress Patterns in Words, and Rhythmic Patterns are among the interactive pronunciation activities available. It also includes a thorough pronunciation guide, as well as listening exercises and quizzes.

5. ManyThings.org

ManyThings.org has a page dedicated to practicing American English pronunciation for ESL students. With Flash and MP3 audio, it provides excellent basic pair practice. The site also has "Listen and Repeat" videos that students can utilize at home to improve their pronunciation.

6. SpokenSkills is number six on the list.

SpokenSkills contains a wealth of materials for ESL students and teachers, but the activities for vowel and consonant sounds are particularly useful for practicing pronunciation.

There are sets of practice words for each sound that students can hear.

They can also record themselves and repeat the process till they're happy with the results. There are additional practice tasks for intonation and minimal pairs.

7. The Learner's Dictionary is number seven.

Merriam-Webster's Learner's Perfect Pronunciation practice activities are included in the Dictionary, with a total of 15 sessions, each with a new set of sounds and five exercises. Students listen to a collection of words that all have the same sound, then repeat each one.

Finally, a quiz is included to assess a student's ability to detect various sounds. Exercises for syllable stress and sentence practice are also available, and they review everything learnt during the lesson.

8. Pictures and Words

And just when you thought there were no more resources for young learners to practice their pronunciation, the BBC comes along with their Words and Pictures site. Little ones may practice consonant and vowel sounds, as well as CVC words, through a range of entertaining, interactive games.

The usage of online tools for improving pronunciation

The Use of Overhead Projectors

Most lecture theatres and seminar rooms have an overhead projector (OHP) and you will certainly have seen them in use. There are however some "Do's" and "Don'ts" when preparing overhead transparencies (OHTs).

- Do use permanent (waterproof) pens if you intend to re-use the

OHT (water soluble inks smudge very easily and detract from your presentation).

- Do leave space to add to the transparency as the lecture develops; do this on an overlay or with water-soluble inks.
- Do use large fonts; it will depend on the size of the lecture theatre but don't use anything smaller than 24 point.
- Do use colour for emphasis – for instance for a heading or key words, but..
- Don't use colours that are difficult to read when projected – red, yellow and orange are particularly unsuitable.
- Don't fill the area available with text. Restrict yourself to key words.
- Don't photocopy text or diagrams from a book straight on to an OHT. The font size will be too small. Enlarge the original first.
- Don't put complex diagrams on OHTs that the audience has to copy – supplement the OHT by giving out printed copies.

For some further tips see Hayes and Campbell (1998).

There are also some basic points to remember when you come to use the OHP in a lecture. These are presentational matters, but can make all the difference to how the audience responds to your talk. These ideas are explored in more detail by Race (1999) some also relate to using PowerPoint (see below).

- Make sure you know how to turn the OHP on/off. Most projectors have a switch that activates a spare bulb in event of failure. Find it.
- Before you start, check that the OHP is correctly aligned and positioned for the screen and that the image is in focus.
- Face the audience – use a pointer or pen on the OHP to draw attention to a particular point (rather than turn away and point to the projected image)
- Try to keep the text relating to the point under discussion at the top of the screen – it is the part most visible to the audience
- Be careful not to remove the OHT before members of the audience have had time to make notes
- Cover part of the OHT if you want to deliver a key point with maximum impact, but....

- Don't make a habit out of revealing text line-by-line (it can be very irritating)

Using PowerPoint

There have been two well-established methods of illustrating then traditional lecture or talk – the 35mm slide projector and the overhead projector (OHP). Each has had its role – for instance 35mm slides allow you to show photographs to illustrate the symptoms characteristic of a particular condition. The OHP enables you to prepare visual material in advance and to build on this as the lecture proceeds.

However computer-based technology has brought a new and powerful tool for clinical teaching – Microsoft PowerPoint. PowerPoint is part of the Microsoft Office suite of programs. Essentially it enables users to create a series of slides on a computer which may then be projected in the lecture theatre using a data projector. It has advantages over both the slide projector and overhead projector.

These include:

- PowerPoint comes with pre-formed templates to help you prepare professional looking and visually stimulating slides.
- Judicial use of colour can help you stimulate interest and emphasise key points. Be aware, however, that what appears attractive on your computer screen can be unreadable when projected.

- Text or diagrams are prepared in advance. A PowerPoint feature called 'animation' allows you to build up an image little by little with ease.

- Photographic images can be incorporated into the presentation as another slide – especially simple if the images are captured on a digital camera. However any image can be scanned into PowerPoint.

- Video clips – for instance to illustrate gait – are also readily included in the presentation.

- You can include hyperlinks to webpages

- Slides you want to appear twice can be duplicated at the click of a mouse button and it is simple to re-order the slides.

- PowerPoint contains a variety of methods of changing from one slide to the next – called 'transitions'. These add to your presentation provided they are used sparingly.

Like all technologies PowerPoint needs a little practice to develop your

skills in using it. However the basics are not difficult especially if you are familiar with other programs in Microsoft Office such as Word. Try answering the questions below, which should help you avoid some of the more common errors for the beginner.

Mini quiz

1. Which font is better for PowerPoint slides – Times New Roman or Arial?
2. What minimum font sizes are suitable for a) Titles on slides and b) Text on slides?
3. How many lines of text should appear on a slide?
4. Should the background be pale (with black or dark coloured text) or dark (with white or pale coloured text)?
5. How do you avoid disaster – for instance when the data projector blows its bulb or the data projector won't read your files/memory stick?

Answers

1. In general it is better to use a sans serif font such as Arial to prevent blurring of the text when it is projected.
2. a) Titles should be in a minimum of 32 point. b) Text should be in a minimum of 28 point.

You may require bigger fonts in a large lecture theatre. If possible check the slides at

the venue in advance to ensure legibility from the back. You may be able to use smaller font if you are presenting to a small group in a seminar room rather than a lecture theatre.

3. Try to avoid more than six or seven lines. Use key words and do not fill the entire slide with text. Don't reduce the font size to fit in more lines – use an extra slide instead.
4. If your lecture is in a dark room use a dark blue or green background with pale text (e.g. pale grey or straw yellow). In a partially dimmed room using a dark coloured font on a pale (and possibly textured) background – but not white - may be helpful if you expect your audience to be taking notes.
5. Never put your complete trust in technology. Use PowerPoint to provide a back up set of your slides.

PowerPoint also includes a number of print options. Particularly useful are those that print either three or six slides to a single A4 page with or without notes. These make ideal handouts if you wish to give your audience the key points of your presentation to take home with them and have space to write notes as you talk.

PowerPoint is not difficult to use and it does bring benefits for teaching pronunciation. The links and books suggested below should help you if you wish to acquire the skills to enable you to prepare your own PowerPoint presentations.

Using Video in Teaching and Learning

Videotape recorders can be used in a number of different ways to enhance teaching in both large groups (lectures) and small groups. The advent of digital versatile discs (DVD) makes video images easier to use in the classroom, since individual clips can be immediately accessed without searching through a length of tape. Video images can also be made available via a website for students to view in their private study time. Below are some suggestions for how you could incorporate video into your teaching.

To illustrate clinical conditions.

It is important that students become familiar with the principle signs and symptoms of common clinical conditions. However these can be made much more memorable if they are illustrated (with consent) by video clips of patients. Movement disorders (e.g. Parkinsonian tremor) are more easily seen than described. Video tape is always available, can be used in lectures on non-clinical sites without inconvenience to patients and (once compiled) will save you time.

To show complex sequences of events.

Animated diagrammatic representations of complex events can be slowed and deconstructed. For instance in the cardiac cycle the relationship between the electrocardiogram, atrial and ventricular contraction and pressure changes, valve opening/closing and heart sounds is made relatively easy for students to assimilate if illustrated by animation. Such material is commercially available at a reasonable cost.

To show clinical skills.

Teaching in the clinical skills laboratory is discussed elsewhere in this paper, however the correct procedure for basic clinical skills (e.g. venesection, suturing) can be shown on video before the students attempt these procedures for themselves.

To stimulate student discussion.

A carefully structured video can be a good starting point for initiating student discussion of important issues in medical practice. For instance a cross-cultural consultation between a GP and a patient can trigger discussion about cultural sensitivity in the conduct of interviews and examinations of patients with particular religious beliefs.

As an aid to consideration of affective skills.

The three main areas of content in the undergraduate medical curriculum are knowledge, skills and attitudes. Of these, attitudes are generally held to be the most problematic – they are difficult to innumerate and explain to students. However, video recordings enable the student to put technical skills into the context of appropriate professional behaviour with respect to attitude. A good example might be a recording of a doctor explaining to a patient what will happen during an unpleasant procedure such as bronchoscopy. Students may be asked to identify aspects of the doctor's behaviour that were helpful for relieving the patient's anxiety.

To provide students with feedback on their performance.

In this application a recording is made of a student undertaking some activity. Afterwards this is reviewed by the student and teacher so that the strengths and weaknesses can be identified with view to improving the student's skills. One good example is the use of simulated patients in learning communication skills. After a five or ten minute interview, the student, teacher and simulated patient (normally an actors trained in feedback skills) can replay the recording and discuss particular aspects. Although perhaps a little daunted initially, most students come to value such feedback. A number of studies have investigated the use of video recording in communication skills. There are a number of advantages in using video recording (rather than just verbal feedback from an observer) which have been well summarised by Kurtz (1998).

Resources for Small Group Teaching

Furniture, space and teaching style

Small group teaching requires different skills and resources from those suitable for the lecture theatre. A good starting point is to consider what sort of small group teaching you are undertaking, and how this relates to the layout of the room. Many seminar rooms are set out with the students in rows, facing the teacher who stands in front of a whiteboard or OHP. This layout prevents the students from interacting with each other without some difficulty and hence discourages group discussion. The student expectation will be that they are there to gain information imparted by the teacher, and the tendency will be for the teaching to become a mini-lecture in nature. However it should not be impossible to re-arrange the furniture if this is not your intention. This arrangement, a U shape, is suitable for "closed" discussions (Mackway-Jones and Walker, 1999). The teacher is still a focus for attention and has access to the OHP or board.

However the students are now able to see each other, and hence engage in discussion which does not have to be passed “through the chair”. The teacher
Students

Teacher Board may also establish good contact with an individual by stepping into the centre of the teaching pronunciation. It is also possible to encourage student active participation, for instance by handing over the pen to a student with the words “Perhaps you would like to show us that on the board.”

Students very quickly adopt the expectation of active participation. A further re-arrangement changes this format from a closed discussion to an “open” discussion.

In this circular arrangement the tutor has relinquished the position of power, and is now a member of the group. The whiteboard may not even be associated with the teachers seating position, but with another member of the group appointed as “scribe”. This arrangement encourages an open discussion where all learn from

participation rather than by teacher-to-student directed learning (the so-called transmitter-receiver model). This arrangement is essential for some activities, such as problem-based learning (see elsewhere in this paper).

Flipcharts and Whiteboards

Flipcharts are a teaching resource well suited to small group teaching (but which are far too small for use in the lecture theatre. In some ways they can be used as a substitute whiteboard (or chalkboard). For instance the group could be asked to brainstorm (“What are the possible causes of chest pain?”), and the tutor records them on the flipchart for later expansion. However they can be used in other ways

to advantage. The group might be divided into two or three smaller groups and asked to consider either the same question or problem, or two or three related ones. Each group is equipped with a page from the flipchart and a pen. After a suitable period for discussion has been allowed the groups are asked to summarise their deliberations and, using the flipchart as a guide, present their findings to the whole group. The various pages might then be attached to the wall with ‘Blu-tack’ for future reference. (The tutor may wish to retain these as a record, or to type them up for distribution.)

A newer relation of the whiteboard is the interactive white board. This is attached to a computer and data projector. What is written on the board (with an electronic stylus) may be stored as a computer file, printed and copied to members of the group.

Summary of the Chapter

This chapter deals with the usage of online resources to improve pronunciation in teaching foreign languages. In this chapter the reader can find many interesting sites and online tools for developing the aspect of pronunciation. So choosing the appropriate online teaching material and resources to present in the classroom is one of the important factors in teaching. Materials should be easy to understand, interesting and so on.

First teachers should teach concrete words and later more abstract ones. It is very nice if teacher gives the information about word him/herself. But students should learn to work independently, and dictionaries are their best friends in this